

THE PROBLEM OF SELECTION OF LEXICAL MATERIAL FOR AVIATION ENGLISH ON REQUIREMENTS OF ICAO

Kushakov Yusup Xaytbayevich

dotsent v.b. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti

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Abstract. *The article examines the specifics of aviation English as a language for special purposes, as well as the features of professionally oriented language training in an aviation university. The principles and criteria for selecting the lexical minimum are presented. Particular attention is paid to the problem of selecting lexical material for the discipline "Aviation English" on the requirements of ICAO. The author highlights the key problems in this sphere.*

Key words: *aviation, basic, communication, development, English, framework, ICAO, language, lexical, material, method*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada aviatsiya ingliz tilining maxsus maqsadlar uchun til sifatida o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, shuningdek, aviatsiya universitetida kasbiy yo'naltirilgan tillarni o'qitish xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Leksik minimumni tanlash tamoyillari va mezonlari keltirilgan. ICAO talablari bo'yicha "Aviation English" fanining leksik materialini tanlash muammosiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Muallif ushbu sohadagi asosiy muammolarni yoritadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *aviatsiya, asosiy, aloqa, rivojlanish, ingliz tili, ramka, ICAO, til, leksik, material, usul*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается специфика авиационного английского языка как языка для специальных целей, а также особенности профессионально-ориентированной языковой подготовки в авиационном вузе. Представлены принципы и критерии отбора лексического минимума. Особое внимание уделено проблеме отбора лексического материала для дисциплины «Авиационный английский язык» по требованиям ИКАО. Автор выделяет ключевые проблемы в этой сфере.*

Ключевые слова: *авиация, базовый, коммуникация, развитие, английский, структура, ИКАО, язык, лексикон, материал, метод.*

ICAO has done a tremendous amount to ensure that its language requirements are implemented, so that many of the problems that arise in this regard are resolved. At the development stage and immediately after the adoption of the requirements, dozens of international conferences were held for managers of various levels, instructors, teachers and raters. In “our” corner of the globe alone, such conferences were held in Minsk, Kyiv, Moscow, Alma-Ata, St. Petersburg, Baku, Ulyanovsk... ICAO, with the help of language experts from many countries, created a digital audio library of examples from real recordings of level confirmation exams, which contain speech samples at absolutely all levels, including “flat” ones, where the same level is set for each element, and more difficult-to-assess recordings, where different elements of language proficiency of the same candidate were assessed at different levels. To this day, the European and North Atlantic Office of ICAO holds (currently in an online format) meetings with interested specialists, where various aspects of language training and testing are discussed. In 2012, ICAO's Montreal headquarters launched a project to have the organization endorse tests used around the world. The process was not free, and many small

organizations did not submit their tests for review. But dozens did participate. Unfortunately, there was no PRICESG member involved in the endorsement, and it seemed that the people who were running the process were either unfamiliar or not familiar at all with the language context - the basis of what people who write and evaluate tests need to understand. It did not work, and after three years the initiative died. Nevertheless, I am still proud of the country and the team of developers who had the opportunity to lead and train raters and examiners: the result of our joint work was the only test created by non-native speakers that was endorsed by ICAO for several years. Aviation English, being a classic example of language for specific purposes (LSP) includes all possible situations of language use by representatives of various professions in the aviation sphere (flight crew members, air traffic controllers, engineers, technicians, etc.). The aviation sphere itself includes such areas as flight operation of aircraft, air traffic control, aircraft maintenance, flight organization, airfield operation, passenger service, etc. According to ICAO Circular 323-AN/185 "Recommendations on Aviation English Language Training Programs", aviation English is a kind of "space", at one pole of which are very specific standardized phraseological "formulas", and at the other - free communication in English on aviation topics. In this context, aviation English has specifics, which are associated with the use of professional standard phraseology, technical terms, and also combines elements of technical, professional and general English [1]. One of the goals of professionally oriented teaching of English is the development of professional foreign language lexical competence. As part of the training process, cadets must achieve a level of mastery of special lexical units of aviation English sufficient to perform professional tasks. If an aviation specialist does not know how to correctly use terminological concepts, makes lexical errors in communication, this invariably leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of communication, and sometimes to a communication failure. It is obvious that inaccuracy in radiotelephone communication poses a real danger to people's lives. After all, any communication failure in the radio between the flight crew and the air traffic controller can lead to serious consequences, such as deviation from the specified course or taking the wrong altitude, and as a result - a dangerous approach of aircraft, a collision, or an air crash. Training in aviation English is ultimately aimed at ensuring flight safety. An indicator of a high level of communicative competence of students is the level of formation of lexical skills, which, in turn, depends on the competence of the teacher of aviation English and the effective selection of the lexical minimum. There is no doubt that teaching aviation English is quite difficult, because there are such concepts as the multifaceted nature of a word, the presence of several meanings, compatibility, the meaning of context. And since aviation English is a "space" covering various areas of aviation, teachers face the difficult task of selecting the appropriate lexical minimum sufficient for performing the professional tasks of a future aviation specialist. Moreover, the selection of the content of educational material on aviation English includes an interdisciplinary block, which involves the use by cadets of knowledge in such disciplines as "Aircraft Design", "Navigation", "Air Law", "Meteorology", "Aircraft Operation", etc. This fact significantly complicates the teacher's work, since he often does not have a technical education. The need to use interdisciplinary links is confirmed by ICAO Document 9835 (Guide to the Implementation of ICAO Language Proficiency Requirements), which notes that training flight crew members and air traffic controllers in aviation language necessarily involves mastering a wider range of language tools covering a wide range of topics related to aviation [2, p. 74]. And the closer the subject content of the course is to real situations, actions, functions and objects that students encounter in their professional activities, the more effective and efficient the course training materials are [1, p. 19]. Document 9835 presents the main lexical domains that aviation

specialists must master. However, this guide was published in 2010, and changes in priorities in science, technology and public life are currently happening very quickly, new technologies, unmanned aerial vehicles are emerging, and new realities and new threats to flight safety are emerging, and accordingly, a layer of new vocabulary appears that is not presented in the document. Therefore, the teacher must supplement the lexical minimum of students independently. Since the accumulation of knowledge and replenishment of the active vocabulary occurs over time, then in the context of teaching aviation English, it is advisable to highlight lexical minimums for assimilation at each stage of training or for each topic. One of the most common tools for working on vocabulary are dictionaries, including the so-called "glossary". In essence, this is a small dictionary, which is a separate part of the textbook, in our case, on aviation English. The textbook itself is the main teaching tool. It determines the technology of the entire educational process in the context of studying aviation English. Most often, dictionary authors are guided by their own experience and an empirical approach when selecting vocabulary for study. However, despite individual differences, the lexical minimum must meet a number of principles. These principles can be conditionally divided into three groups: 1. Statistical principles should be based on frequency and prevalence indicators, as well as the usage of lexical units (words). 2. Methodological principles take into account the goal, stage of training, sphere and topic. 3. Linguistic principles include: - the principle of compatibility (the inclusion of a word in the linguistic minimum is determined by its ability to form combinations with other words); - the principle of stylistic unlimitedness (the word must belong to the neutral, literary, colloquial, bookish-written styles of the language); - the principle of word-formation value (the word must form derivative forms in other parts of speech); - the principle of polysemy of a word; - the principle of structural ability (the word must perform not only lexical but also grammatical function); - the principle of frequency; - the principle of semantic value (the words studied must be related to the specialty and most often encountered in professional literature). It is due to the principle of semantic value that the number of lexical units included in the minimum can be reduced to exclusively functionally significant words. However, even rarely used but significant words in the profession are included in the minimum. Also, the lexical minimum can include words related to the "language of the profession" - narrow terms, jargon and professionalisms. An integration criterion that involves the selection of lexical units based on the belonging of lexical units to different specialized academic disciplines. Using the above principles of selecting lexical units for study, it is worth considering that the lexical minimum of the language of the specialty has its own characteristics and tasks and contains words that ensure mastery of the language of the specialty. The selection of vocabulary for textbooks and teaching aids on aviation English is a complex task due to the fact that teachers have to be guided not only by the principles described in the article, but also take into account the specifics of aviation English. The criteria for identifying the subject area and the depth of classification should be determined by the nature of the problems to be solved [3, p. 88]. All selected lexical units must be truly necessary, and most importantly, relevant for ensuring professional communication. It is advisable to try to assess the relevance of the selected topic for the near future [2. p. 75]. Moreover, given the interdisciplinary connections of aviation English with professional disciplines, when selecting the lexical minimum or compiling thematic dictionaries, one should seek an expert assessment or translation accuracy from specialists in these specialized disciplines. This aspect contributes to the formation of systemic knowledge through the establishment of interdisciplinary connections, which are the most important basis in the system of professional education [5].

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